

A high-level visual modelling environment for parallel geospatial (raster) processing workflows

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The demand for parallel processing capabilities has increased rapidly over the past 15 years or so, driven by ever higher spatial and temporal resolution of raster data, e.g. derived from LiDAR or satellite data. Meanwhile, GIS support multithreaded processing of selected algorithms, and libraries for high-level programming languages, such as 'Dask' for Python or 'parallel' for R, support the development of parallel processing workflows. However, while these libraries greatly facilitate the development of parallel geospatial processing workflows, they still require decent programming skills. Graphical GIS model builders, e.g. in ArcGIS or QGIS, currently do not support the development of scalable (task-) parallel workflows.

In this demo, we present the extension of the LUMASS visual programming environment for the development of parallel geospatial (raster) processing workflows that only requires the understanding of high-level programming and parallel workflow design principles. The workflows are scalable and run on shared-memory laptops and workstations as well as on distributed-memory compute clusters with thousands of cores. The framework supports pipeline, data, and task parallelism, and users can easily convert sequential to parallel workflows as long as input-data independence is ensured.

While the framework's core processing components are mainly focused on processing (multi-dimensional) raster data, arbitrary command-line tools, scripts, and programs can be seamlessly integrated into the workflow to augment its processing capabilities. This enables GIS analysts, scientists, professionals, and students with little to no programming skills to easily develop geospatial parallel (raster) processing workflows.